

Editorial

From The Desk of Guest Editor.....

Within the last few decades, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has become a world-wide problem and constitutes a major threat to public health. AMR has increased as a result of widespread use of antimicrobials providing greater opportunity for bacteria to exchange genetic material, allowing resistant genes to spread between bacterial populations and rendering antimicrobials ineffective for their intended use. The inappropriate prescribing of antimicrobials by the healthcare professions is a major concern to be addressed, especially as fewer and fewer new antimicrobials are being developed.

The benefits of prescribing antimicrobials to treat or prevent infections are limited by a number of problems associated with their use, e.g. side effects, toxicity, allergic reactions and importantly, the development of resistant strains of microbes. Indications for the use of systemic antibiotics in dentistry are limited because most dental and periodontal diseases are best managed by operative intervention and hygiene measures.

Dentists should not prescribe medicines other than to meet the identified dental needs of patients. They must make an appropriate assessment of the patient's condition, prescribe within their experience and competence, and keep accurate records of the treatment.

The increasing resistance problems of recent years are probably related to the over or misuse of broad-spectrum agents. Dentists can make a difference by the judicious use of antimicrobials - prescribing the correct drug, at the standard dosage and appropriate regimen - only when systemic spread of infection is evident. There is a clear need for the development of prescribing guidelines and educational initiatives to encourage the rational and appropriate use of drugs in dentistry.

This guidance has been developed to promote judicious antimicrobial prescribing and antimicrobial stewardship within dentistry. Antimicrobial stewardship has been defined broadly as a coherent set of

actions to promote responsible use of antimicrobials. This necessitates organisational or healthcare-wide systems to promote and monitor responsible and appropriate use of antimicrobials to preserve their future effectiveness.

Irresponsible or inappropriate use of antimicrobials include:

- Prescribing in the absence of an infection or where local measures will suffice.
- Prescribing prophylactically when not indicated.
- An incorrect dose or too long or short duration.
- An unnecessarily broad spectrum or narrow spectrum antimicrobial or wrong antimicrobial for the microbiology of a specific infection.
- Use of IV when oral route can be used.
- Choosing an incorrect antimicrobial for a patient with a known allergy.
- Antimicrobial stewardship is about safe and effective use; prescribing the right antibiotic antimicrobial for the right clinical indication, at the right time, dose and route with minimal toxicity and minimal impact of subsequent resistance to the patient and future patients.
- Antibiotics play an essential role in the treatment of oral infections, but their use should be carefully evaluated to prevent bacterial resistance. By practicing responsible prescribing, we can help to preserve the effectiveness of antibiotics for future generations.

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